

On-chip signature-based functional test of RF blocks using two-tone response envelope analysis

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Abstract This work presents a novel and low-cost methodology for testing embedded RF blocks. It is based on the detection and analysis of the two-tone response envelope of the device under test (DUT). This envelope signal is processed to obtain a digital signature sensitive to key specifications of the DUT. An optimized regression model is used to relate the digital signatures to the target specifications. The proposed test procedure is studied from an analytical point of view, and a demonstrator has been developed to prove the feasibility of the approach. This demonstrator features a 2.445GHz low-power LNA and a simple envelope detector, and has been developed in a 90nm CMOS technology. Electrical simulation of the extracted view verify the functionality of the proposed test technique.

Keywords RF test · RF BIST · Signature test

1 Introduction

Nowadays complete and very complex systems are integrated on one single die. By far the largest portion of that is in the digital part of the system, which usually contains Multi-core GHz Processors, multiple Mbytes of memory, Media Access Controllers (MAC) and several dedicated Digital Signal Processors (DSP). Examples can be found in consumer applications like Cellular phones, DVD players, Multi-media players and so on. A general conceptual scheme for the architectures of these present and future systems can be that in Figure 1, where any wireless-based application is conceptually covered. As shown in the typical example of Figure 1, these systems usually contain one or multiple Analog Front-Ends (AFE), Analog Back-Ends (ABE), as well as RF Receive and Transmit functions.

From a test engineer point of view, testing RF subsystems embedded in a complex, tightly-integrated SoC represents a challenging task. The difficulty stems from the fact that

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Fig. 1 Generic SoC view

each RF block has a specific set of diverse specifications that usually require a custom test strategy. It can be said that RF testing has inherited all the difficulties of analog testing, but adding also the problem of handling high frequency signals. This framework leads to the same fundamental problem for analog and RF testing: these blocks are tested based on the functional measurement of a set of specifications, while fault-model-based test, very successful in the digital test domain, are impossible to standardize in the RF field, since each circuit type demands its own custom fault model.

The diverse specifications and high operating frequency of RF blocks, as well as the large impact of process variations in current deep sub-micron technologies, make necessary extensive tests that are complex and expensive to perform. Reducing RF test complexity and cost is still an open research topic that has been addressed in a number of different approaches. Recent work in this area includes defect modeling and failure diagnosis [Acar and Ozev(2005a), Acar and Ozev(2005b), Heutmaker and Le(1999), Halder et al(2005)Halder, Bhattacharya, Srinivasan, and Chatterjee], alternate test [Halder et al(2005)Halder, Bhattacharya, Srinivasan, and Chatterjee, Voorakaranam et al(2002)Voorakaranam, Cherubal, and Chatterjee], DfT and BIST techniques [Yin et al(2005)Yin, Eisenstadt, Fox, and Zhang, Ryu et al(2006)Ryu, Kim, and Sylla, Gopalan et al(2005)Gopalan, Das, Washburn, and Mukund, Valdes-Garcia et al(2006)Valdes-Garcia, Silva-Martinez, and Sanchez-Sinencio, Valdes-Garcia et al(2007)Valdes-Garcia, Khalil, Bakkaloglu, Silva-Martinez, and Sanchez-Sinencio, Akbay and Chatterjee(2005), Kulhalli et al(2004)Kulhalli, Seth, and Fu], etc.

In particular, BIST techniques have been identified as a solution to mitigate RF test drawbacks for several reasons [Valdes-Garcia et al(2006)Valdes-Garcia, Silva-Martinez, and Sanchez-Sinencio]:

- The test cost of RF systems is dominated by expensive automatic test equipment (ATE). Thence it should be desirable to move some of the testing functions to the test board or to the device under test (DUT) itself.
- There is a strong demand of known-good-die test solutions that can be implemented at wafer level, due mainly to the increasing packaging costs.

- BIST can be used to identify faulty blocks inside the system, providing a valuable information for yield enhancement and accelerating product development.

This work describes a new technique that can be used to improve the testability of RF blocks embedded in integrated transceivers. It is based on the detection and analysis of the two-tone response envelope of an RF block by determining a digital signature that can be easily related to the circuit functional specs. The envelope response signal is extracted using a simple envelope detector. Then, the need of RF test equipment is eliminated since the response envelope is a low frequency signal compared to the operating frequency of the tested device and it is handled by digital means. This work is organized as follows. Section II reviews previous relevant work on RF testing. Then, Section III presents the proposed test technique. Section IV discusses its on-chip implementation and presents the design of an integrated demonstrator. After that, Section V provides some relevant experimental results to validate the proposal. Finally, Section VI summarizes the main contributions of this work.

2 Review of previous work

Direct approaches for testing and diagnosing an RF device are based on the application of a high-frequency stimulus to the DUT, and the observation of its response. This requires the use of high-speed external test equipment and, for embedded RF devices, the provision of an adequate test access. However, the increase in operation frequency and integration capabilities turns the latter two requirements quite difficult. Test access to internal nodes is usually impossible, and even in the case these nodes are reachable, there may be electrical losses in the transport of the signals from the chip to the external tester due to their inherent high-frequency.

Some authors [Voorakaranam et al(2002)Voorakaranam, Cherubal, and Chatterjee, Ferrario et al(2003)Ferrario, Wolf, Moss, and Slamani] replicate traditional RF test equipment such as spectrum analyzers on a load board. These approaches employ complex circuitry (mixers, frequency synthesizer, etc.) for up- and down-conversion of the test stimulus and its response, respectively. The need of RF testers is eliminated and multiple RF test specifications can be extracted. However, the load board circuitry is too complex for its direct BIST implementation, and hence this approach is limited to the test of discrete RF circuits.

The approach in [Acar and Ozev(2005a), Acar and Ozev(2005b)] focuses on failure diagnosis of RF circuits. The work in [Acar and Ozev(2005a)] considers the detection of catastrophic faults, while that in [Acar and Ozev(2005b)] also attempts to isolate parametric ones. Although behavioral simulations demonstrate high fault coverage, they lack a general fault model. Furthermore, it is necessary the use of standard RF test equipment and techniques to enable failure diagnosis.

Loop-back test and diagnosis of transceivers have also been widely explored [Heutmaker and Le(1999), Halder et al(2005)Halder, Bhattacharya, Srinivasan, and Chatterjee, Valdes-Garcia et al(2006)Valdes-Garcia, Silva-Martinez, and Sanchez-Sinencio, Valdes-Garcia et al(2007)Valdes-Garcia, Khalil, Bakkaloglu, Silva-Martinez, and Sanchez-Sinencio]. The main advantage is that only-digital signals are involved as well as that both the receiver and the transmitter are tested at once. However, an on-chip implementation is not so simple since, in practice, some components need to be removed for testing, namely the band-pass filter, close to the antenna, and the power amplifier in the transmission path [Vazquez et al(2005)Vazquez, Huertas, Luque, Barragan, Leger, Rueda, and Huertas].

The use of test sensors embedded into the RF system has also been proposed [Yin et al(2005)Yin, Eisenstadt, Fox, and Zhang, Ryu et al(2006)Ryu, Kim, and Sylla, Gopalan

et al(2005)Gopalan, Das, Washburn, and Mukund, Valdes-Garcia et al(2006)Valdes-Garcia, Silva-Martinez, and Sanchez-Sinencio, Valdes-Garcia et al(2007)Valdes-Garcia, Khalil, Bakkaloglu, Silva-Martinez, and Sanchez-Sinencio, Akbay and Chatterjee(2005), Kulhalli et al(2004)Kulhalli, Seth, and Fu]. Several built-in test schemes have been reported that use integrated peak, root-mean-square (RMS), and power detectors for testing discrete RF modules or complete transceivers. However, these sensors deliver a DC signal. To extract the test specifications from the limited information of a DC magnitude, multiple detectors and/or test configurations have to be used, thus increasing the complexity of the test as well as the required area overhead. Likewise, the design of these detectors is not always straightforward.

In this context, the approaches in [Han et al(2007)Han, Bhattacharya, and Chatterjee, Barragan et al(2010a)Barragan, Fiorelli, Vazquez, Rueda, and Huertas, Abdallah et al(2010)Abdallah, Stratigopoulos, Kelma, and Mir, Barragan et al(2010b)Barragan, Fiorelli, Vazquez, Rueda, and Huertas] propose the use of a simple envelope detector for RF test purposes. The work in [Han et al(2007)Han, Bhattacharya, and Chatterjee] demonstrates that selected specifications can be extracted from the envelope of the response of an RF block to an optimized test stimulus. The envelope signal is acquired with a conventional A/D converter and processed to carry out the demanded measurement. The work in [Abdallah et al(2010)Abdallah, Stratigopoulos, Kelma, and Mir] combines envelope extraction and other sensors, such as Die-Level Process Monitors (DLPM [Zjajo et al(2007)Zjajo, Asian, and de Gyvez]), DC probes, and current sensors, and analyzes how the combined outputs of these sensors correlate to the specifications of the RF DUT.

On the other hand, the work reported by the authors in [Barragan et al(2010b)Barragan, Fiorelli, Vazquez, Rueda, and Huertas] takes advantage of analytical results to define a digital signature from the envelope of the response of the DUT to a two-tone at-speed test stimulus. This work shows that this digital signature can be easily discriminated when the circuit is performing within specifications. The latter method has some benefits in terms of simplicity. Thus, compared to [Han et al(2007)Han, Bhattacharya, and Chatterjee], there is no need of complex stimulus optimization, processing the envelope is greatly simplified, and the use of a complete A/D converter for signal acquisition is avoided. Also, compared to [Abdallah et al(2010)Abdallah, Stratigopoulos, Kelma, and Mir] a single envelope detector is used instead of multiple sensors, test access to internal nodes of the DUT is not required, and there is no transport of analog DC signals to the outside world, being the test output a simple digital word. However, compared to [Han et al(2007)Han, Bhattacharya, and Chatterjee] and [Abdallah et al(2010)Abdallah, Stratigopoulos, Kelma, and Mir], reference [Barragan et al(2010b)Barragan, Fiorelli, Vazquez, Rueda, and Huertas] has the important disadvantage of not providing functional measurements. The proposal to be described herein aims to extend our previous idea of a signature-based test by a two-tone response envelope characterization. This work will demonstrate how the information contained in the digital signatures can be easily related to the functional specifications of the DUT, while keeping the simplicity of the approach reported in [Barragan et al(2010b)Barragan, Fiorelli, Vazquez, Rueda, and Huertas].

3 Proposed approach

3.1 Theoretical basis

Figure 2-a shows a standard two-tone test set-up that is traditionally used to characterize RF systems. In this test scheme, two high-frequency close tones are used as test stimuli

Fig. 2 a) Traditional two-tone test; b) Two-tone response envelope detection.

and fed to the DUT. The system response is then acquired and conveniently processed to characterize the DUT. Important performance parameters such as forward gain, third-order intercept, inter-modulation products, 1dB compression point, etc, can be measured using this traditional set-up. However, the direct acquisition and processing of the test response is a challenging task, since this response is a high-frequency signal that has to be handled by expensive RF test equipment. Our approach, represented in Figure 2-b, is in fact similar to the traditional scheme, but in this case the DUT response is driving an envelope detector. The extracted envelope has relevant information about the test response at much lower frequencies, this information being easily extracted by simplified processing. Let us consider the typical two-tone test (see 2-a), in which a non-linear RF device is driven by a signal $x(t)$ composed of two equal-magnitude tones at different, but very close, frequencies, in the form,

$$x(t) = A_i \cos\left(\left(\omega_0 - \frac{\omega_g}{2}\right)t\right) + A_i \cos\left(\left(\omega_0 + \frac{\omega_g}{2}\right)t\right) \quad (1)$$

where A_i is the amplitude of each test tone, and ω_g is the frequency difference between them ($\omega_g \ll \omega_0$). In order to make an analytical study, a third-order non-linear model has been assumed for the RF block. That is, the response $y(t)$ of the system can be written as,

$$y(t) = \alpha_1 x(t) + \alpha_3 x^3(t) \quad (2)$$

Expanding (2), and discarding the out-of-band components, the response $y(t)$ can be expressed as,

$$y(t) = A_{o1} \cos\left(\left(\omega_0 - \frac{\omega_g}{2}\right)t\right) + A_{o1} \cos\left(\left(\omega_0 + \frac{\omega_g}{2}\right)t\right) + A_{o3} \cos\left(\left(\omega_0 - \frac{3\omega_g}{2}\right)t\right) + A_{o3} \cos\left(\left(\omega_0 + \frac{3\omega_g}{2}\right)t\right) \quad (3)$$

Then, let $R(t)$ be the envelope of the response signal $y(t)$. Using the Rice formulation [Dugundji(1958)], $R(t)$ can be derived as,

$$R(t) = \left| 2A_{o1} \cos\left(\frac{\omega_g}{2}t\right) + 2A_{o3} \cos\left(\frac{3\omega_g}{2}t\right) \right| \quad (4)$$

Signal $R(t)$ results to be a periodic function with period $T_g = 2\pi/\omega_g$. Given that $\omega_g \ll \omega_0$, then signal $R(t)$ results to be a low frequency signal that still contain information about the magnitude of the spectral components, A_{o1} and A_{o3} , of the high-frequency DUT response. In this work, we take advantage of this information to define a simple signature that can be used for testing purposes.

3.2 Signature definition and efficient implementation of the signature extractor

In order to extract a meaningful test signature from the response envelope signal $R(t)$, some considerations have to be made. The target signature has to keep the information about the DUT response contained in the envelope, that is, magnitudes A_{o1} and A_{o3} , but also the computation of the signature itself has to be as simple as possible to reduce the overhead due to the signature extractor. In this line, this work proposes the computation of the area under the $R(t)$ curve as a simple test signature, that, as it will be shown, can be efficiently computed on-chip while keeping the desired information.

The area, \hat{J} , under one period of the response envelope $R(t)$ can be easily computed as,

$$\hat{J} = \int_0^{T_g} R(t) dt = \frac{8}{\omega_g} \left(A_{o1} - \frac{A_{o3}}{3} \right) \quad (5)$$

Signature \hat{J} results to be a linear combination of the high-frequency response spectral components A_{o1} , and A_{o3} . Consequently, it should be clear that signature is sensitive to changes in gain and non-linearity specifications, so any deviation affecting those characteristics would affect also its value.

A traditional approach for computing signature \hat{J} in the digital domain would require a precise A/D converter to acquire the response envelope signal, and an arithmetic DSP. Instead of that, since the response envelope is a low-frequency periodic signal, the computation of signature can be made using an alternative method; in our proposal, by using a simplification of the efficient test core for periodic analog signal analysis presented by the authors in [Vazquez et al(2005)Vazquez, Huertas, Luque, Barragan, Leger, Rueda, and Huertas]. Figure 3 shows the block diagram of our proposed signature extractor. It takes advantage of the noise-shaping characteristics of first-order $\Sigma\Delta$ -modulators to accurately compute in the digital domain. Signal $R(t)$ is directly fed to a first-order $\Sigma\Delta$ -modulator, which provides a simple and robust A/D conversion without the need of a full A/D interface. Its output bit-stream, d , is then integrated using a simple digital counter to get a digital signature J . This signature is given by,

Fig. 3 Block diagram of the proposed signature extractor.

$$J = \sum_{n=1}^{MN} = \frac{8MN}{\pi} \left(A_{o1} - \frac{A_{o3}}{3} \right) \pm 2 \quad (6)$$

where N is the oversampling ratio in the modulator defined as $N = T_g/T_s$ (T_s is the sampling period in the modulator), the integration has been extended to M envelope response periods, and magnitudes A_{o1} and A_{o3} are in this case normalized with respect to the full-scale range of the $\Sigma\Delta$ modulator. It is important to notice that the error term ± 2 , given by the quantization error in the modulator, does not scale with the number of evaluated samples because this error is naturally compensated when it is integrated by the counter.

Signature J is a digital measurement of the area under the envelope signal, \hat{J} , and the resources needed to calculate it are reduced to a first-order $\Sigma\Delta$ modulator and a simple digital counter.

In a first approximation, the analytical expression (6) could be used to directly compute magnitudes A_{o1} and A_{o3} , and hence, provide a functional characterization of the DUT. However, let us recall that this analysis has been performed under the assumption of a third-order polynomial model for the RF block. Actual DUT behavior may deviate from this idealization, and consequently the analysis becomes more complex, or impossible to complete. In spite of that, the previous analysis is important because we have demonstrated that there is a relation between the proposed signature and performance figures. In this work we extract functional information about the DUT from the proposed signature by building a blind regression model, without assuming any analytical model for the DUT.

3.3 Ensemble Learning

Machine-learning, regression modeling, function approximation, data mining, all this terminology belongs to the vast mathematical field of statistics. Researchers have been struggling to develop the best modeling approach from more than a hundred years. Unfortunately, the idea of best model is always relative to the application and nobody has come out with the definitive approach. Some models perform better on low-dimension spaces, other require few training samples, etc. Actually, the task of model selection has already been investigated (see Chapter 7 in [Hastie et al(2009)Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman]), and a number of criteria have been developed to assess model quality, usually in terms of expected prediction error. Anyhow, managing these concepts is not an easy task to the profane. As a matter of fact most papers that apply machine-learning algorithms to circuit testing usually do not justify the choice of their statistical tool.

In this context, the concept of ensemble learning is very appealing because it builds a mosaic model from a collection of statistical tools. It implements a routine that trains different models using cross-validation principles to deduce the expected prediction error. The final model is a weighted average of a subset of all the trained models, being the weights a function of the calculated prediction error.

We use a Matlab toolbox developed by Wichard and Merkwirth [Wichard et al(2003)Wichard, Ogorzalek, and Merkwirth], which itself uses elements of [Norgaard et al(2002)Norgaard, Ravn, and Poulsen]. Let us briefly present the different models that can be trained by the toolbox.

Linear and Polynomial models The most straightforward model is the linear one. The linear model expresses the measurement vector – in our case the main specifications of the LNA – as a linear combination of the input vectors – in our case the digital signatures. The regression is performed in the least-square sense. The validity range of linear models is usually limited as they are not able to capture non-linear interactions. The results are usually highly biased but present rather low variability, and the generalization error is usually quite close to the training error. Conceptually, the bias is potentially high because the model imposes a strong constraint on the relationship between the measurement vector and the input vectors (i.e. linearity). On the other hand, this strong constraint also ensures that no unreasonable outlier will be produced by the model. In particular, if the model is exercised out of the training range, it may still lead to reasonable asymptotical results, which is not the case for more flexible models.

A simple modification of linear model is the polynomial model. Here the number of input vectors is extended by adding the product of two or more input vectors. Taking into account these new vectors, a linear regression is then performed. Obviously, this approach is better suited for input spaces of low dimensions. Otherwise, even considering low order polynomials terms would lead to a large number of input vectors. The toolbox limits the polynomial degree to the lowest order that generates a number of variables higher than a given threshold. In our case, we have 18 variables and the polynomial is limited to the 3rd degree. A forward stepwise algorithm then searches all the variables among the available ones that improve fitting and add them to the pool of useful variables on a step by step basis. Then, a backward stepwise algorithm tries to remove one variable at a time to avoid redundancy and overfitting.

Nearest-neighbors In a sense, Nearest-Neighbors approaches are the complete opposite to linear modeling. In this approach, no implicit structure is supposed in the data and the model prediction is more an interpolation of the training data than the result of a given function. The prediction for a given input is simply equal to the value of the nearest neighbor in the training set. As a result, Nearest neighbors approaches must store the complete training set in order to make further predictions. The result is a model with low bias but high variability. This means that it adapts very well to local fluctuations but on the other hand is very sensitive to the non-ideality of the available data like noise, outliers or simply density. Indeed, it appears obvious that the larger the training set – which supposedly samples the input space adequately – the better the results. This is particularly troublesome in high-dimensional spaces. Refinements of the method usually rely on defining a larger neighborhood and considering some kind of weighted average (accordingly to a given kernel, for instance Gaussian or Epanechnikovs kernel). It is also possible to adapt the size of the neighborhood to the local sampling density to mitigate the effects of noise and outliers in regions with sparse data. The

toolbox uses a genetic algorithm to select the optimal methodology, varying the number of nearest neighbors and also the metric used for distance calculation and for local weighting.

Neural Networks The field of function approximation through Neural Networks is very extended and many different networks topologies have been investigated. The toolbox implements two families of Neural Networks. The first family is that of the well-known Perceptron Networks, which involve only feedforward layers of neurons. The multilayer perceptrons can be trained with either 1st order or 2nd order gradient decent. The second family is that of Radial Basis Function Networks. While Perceptron networks use linear or sigmoid activation functions for regression, RBF networks use radial activation functions that are parameterized at least by their centers and radii. Several training algorithm exist that give different results. The best known training method is the Expectation Maximization (EM) algorithm which optimizes an initial guess. A simplified version of it is the David MacKay (DM) algorithm, which is faster but has no formal proof of convergence. And finally the combination of Regression Trees with RBF network [Orr(1999)] has given good results. A regression tree is grown to split the input space in smaller hyperrectangles which will then determine the center and size of the RBFs. The size of the tree is limited by a parameter that defines the minimum number of samples in a split. Furthermore, the complexity of the model is then reduced by pruning which is done by forward selection and can be combined with backward elimination. Finally, Perceptron Radial Basis Function Nets (PRBFN) [Cohen and Intrator(2002)] are, as its name indicates, a neural network with hidden layers composed of a mixture of perceptron and RBF units. The motivation of this approach is that it has been shown that a function can be decomposed into exclusive radial and projection parts. The RBF units thus tend to capture the radial components while the ridge (perceptron) units try to reproduce the projection part.

Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines The MARS approach proposed by Friedman [Friedman(1991)] has been used successfully in a large number of papers in the past few years [Voorakaranam et al(2007)Voorakaranam, Akbay, Bhattacharya, Cherubal, and Chatterjee, Variyam et al(2002)Variyam, Cherubal, Chatterjee, Inc, and Dallas,Senguttuvan et al(2009)Senguttuvan, Bhattacharya, and Chatterjee]. As its name indicates, it is based on common regression splines. For high-dimensional data, only low-order splines are considered (typically lower than three)in order to limit the complexity of the model. The Adaptive Multivariate part of the name comes from the recursive partitioning of the input space, in a way very similar to the regression tree used for RBF networks previous subsection. This kind of model presents the advantage of being continuous with continuous derivatives, a constraint which may be a desirable feature and which contributes to reduce the variability of the model prediction. Moreover, MARS models consider additive contributions of either local or global interactions but always between few variables at a time. This structure makes easier to extract diagnosis information from the model.

4 Demonstrator design

The implemented demonstrator is depicted in Fig. 4. This proof-of-concept prototype consists of an LNA with a built-in envelope detector, designed in a 90nm CMOS technology. The aim of this demonstrator is to verify the feasibility of the discussed test procedure. Because of that, the signature extractor in FIG will not be integrated. It will be emulated externally, which provides a greater flexibility in the validation. The designed LNA is a

Fig. 4 Schematic of the designed LNA jointly with the envelope detector.

single-ended LNA with inductive source degeneration. It is specified to work under the IEEE 802.15.4 protocol. It has been designed to have a noise figure (NF) below 5dB, and a third-order input intercept point (IIP3) higher than -6dBm with both source and load impedances equal to 50ω . Its power consumption is 1.44mW with a V_{DD} voltage of 1.2V. Transistor M_1 is designed to be under moderate inversion to reduce power consumption, capacitor C_{ext} is used to adjust input impedance without spoil the NF and L_d is chosen to obtain the higher gain available for this design.

We have developed a simple current-mode envelope detector adapted from [Cha et al(2009)Cha, Woo, Cho, Park, Lee, Kim, and Laskar]. It comprises a voltage-to-current converter (VIC) followed by an AC-coupled half-wave current-mode rectifier with a passive output low-pass filter. The selected VIC is a simple CMOS push-pull inverter with resistive source degeneration. Qualitatively, the half-wave rectifier works as follows: when the VIC output current flows into the rectifier, the diode-connected transistor M_5 is turned on and M_6 is off, so no current is drawn by M_b and $v_{0,Rect}$ is zero. Oppositely, when the VIC output current leaves the rectifier, M_5 turns off while M_6 and M_a turn on, and this current is mirrored through M_b to the RC low pass filter. The RC constant has been adjusted to reject the high frequency carrier, so the output voltage, $v_{0,Rect}$, follows the envelope of the input signal.

LNA and envelope detector have been co-designed to optimize the overall operation. All designed transistors are sized with minimum length to obtain the best high frequency performance. LNA bias circuit is not shown in Fig.4 for clarity. Voltage $V_{DC,Rect}$ is used to bias transistor M_6 in the subthreshold region.

The described envelope detector fulfills the following five conditions. Firstly, its input impedance is high enough to discard modifications in the output matching entailing losses in the output power. Secondly, it has low power consumption both not to generate a temperature gradient and maintain the LNA transistors' characteristics, and to allow the utilization of the BIT block under LNA normal operation without considerable current overhead. Also, the envelope detector has an independent power supply to be turned off when test is not performed. Moreover the test block has enough dynamic range to perform the needed variations in the input signal amplitude. Finally, the area overhead is very small.

Fig. 5 Layout of the LNA with the envelope detector.

Characteristics	LNA without envelope detector	LNA with codesigned envelope detector
Gain (dB)	12.4	12.4
NF (dB)	3.66	3.65
IIP3 (dBm)	-1.24	-1.40
S11 (dB)	-24.0	-24.9
S22 (dB)	-9.6	-10.5
S12	-26.3	-26.4
$Z_{in}(\omega)$	46.6-13.2j	45.0-12.0j
$Z_{out}(\omega)$	44.3+12.8j	44.0+10.0j

Table 1 LNA characteristics with and without envelope detector.

The complete layout of the prototype is shown in Fig. 5. The total area without pads is 760 μ m x 700 μ m. The area of the rectifier is 100 μ m x 130 μ m. The area overlay is 2.4%. However this area overhead can also be considered as zero because the LNA area, especially because of its three inductors, has enough free and unused space to permit the insertion of the detector.

Table 1 lists the typical characteristics of the designed LNA with and without the BIT block, obtained by post-layout simulation. As it can be appreciated, no substantial differences exist in the results.

Fig. 6 shows the large-signal transfer curve of the envelope detector obtained by post-layout simulation.

Fig 7.a shows the output waveform of the envelope detector when it is excited by two 50mV tones at 2.4445GHz and 2.4455GHz (7.b). Both the input and output waveforms in the figures have been normalized to their respective maximum values. As it can be clearly visualized, the output of the rectifier follows the envelope of its input signal. The envelope signal reaches a peak value of approximately 180 mV.

Fig. 6 Transference of the envelope detector injecting an input tone of 2.445GHz.

Fig. 7 a) Normalized output of the envelope detector and b) normalized output of the LNA with an LNA input of two tones.

5 Experimental results

The J -signature defined in section III is used to predict the performance figures of the LNA using the ensemble learning paradigm previously described. For this purpose, a set of 100 instances of the demonstrator was obtained by a post-layout Monte-Carlo simulation. Out of the 100 instances, 90 were used to train the ensemble, while 10 randomly chosen instances were taken apart as test set to verify the accuracy of the prediction. A set of different signatures J_{LNA} was extracted varying the magnitude of the input test tones. In addition, given that the envelope detector in the demonstrator is subject to the same variation mechanisms as the LNA, the test stimuli were bypassed to the envelope detector and signatures J_{env} were

evaluated from the resulting envelope signal. Signatures J_{env} allow the ensemble model to estimate and remove the contribution of the envelope detector variations. Two different two-tone test stimuli were used in our validation, corresponding to magnitudes $A_i = 29dBm$ and $A_i = 26dBm$. Both test stimuli were centred around $f_0 = 2.445GHz$ (the peak-gain frequency of the LNA) and the frequency gap between the two tones was set to $f_g = 1MHz$.

Since the signature extractor was not included in this first proof-of-concept prototype, a realistic verilogA model was used to compute the test signatures for the obtained envelope signals. The oversampling ratio and the number of evaluation periods were set to $N=144$, and $M=1$, respectively. This way, we obtain a set of four independent signatures to feed the ensemble model, i.e. a pair (J_{LNA}, J_{env}) is computed for each test stimulus.

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